

Interview Guide

The following questions guided the conversation with the SMEs. The goal was to prepare beforehand questions to drive the interview without being strict; these were grouped by categories, ensuring a more comprehensive range of topics with different emotions associated (e.g., do not focus only on the positive or negative aspects).

Introduction The goal of the first questions was to “break the ice” and introduce the topic.

- For how long do you work at this company? How long in the role of team lead/tech lead?
- In the past, we worked with Jenkins and SVN, and since the last year, we moved to Gitlab, at least for the projects in the new stack. Do you think this move was an improvement in the developer experience productivity and the way we deliver our software?

Positive Questions to drive the people to highlight the favourable aspects of their methodology.

- What are the good things/positive points about our current delivery flow?

Neutral A set of questions without any extreme negative or positive weights, which have the goal of promoting the description of the current process.

- What are the stages that identify your delivery flow?
- What is the best way to describe your delivery flow?
 1. A straight way from a commit to production? (1 feature → 1 path to production)
 2. A few loops that are joined to be sent to destination (Production).
 3. A train that joins a huge number of commits/features until finally the destination has arrived to production.
- Do you agree with the current state of your delivery flow? (showing the model first)
- Do you have any methodology/process to review your delivery process?
- We moved from a trunk-based development approach to a feature branch approach with Gitlab. Do you think this is a way to secure our delivery flow or simply a way to add more layers?
- What can influence the lead time (time from commit until production?)

- Do you think the fact our branches allow us to deploy until UAT allows us to save time?
- Do you think it's easy to explain to your stakeholders (e.g. business) the stages we have (from commit to Production)?

Negative Questions to discuss around pain points and aspects that need improvement.

- What are the sources of inefficiency and pain points of our delivery flow?
- Any improvement areas that appear on the top of your mind?

Controversial Specific questions that focus on the interactions and processes shared with other teams.

- Do you think top management or business teams are influencing/compromising the delivery flow?
- Do you think that other teams (e.g., teams other than Engineering) trust our ability to deliver with quality?
- Do you think there are people that still don't see the value of Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery?
- Do you think we will ever have continuous deployment? (commits that reach production automatically)

Future Questions around to what's next.

- In your perspective, what is the future? What can we do to deliver value to customers quicker and with quality?
- Do you think we need to define benchmarks for our process and waiting times?
- Do you think we need metrics to follow the process; do you imagine any type of metric?